

A technique to retrieve vertical concentration profiles of individual aerosol species based on the synergy of lidar and spectrophotometer measurements.

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Abstract: In this study, we present the concept of a synergistic algorithm to retrieve the vertical concentration profiles of individual aerosol species using lidar and spectrophotometer measurements. Synergies among the following instruments will be deployed: a depolarization Raman lidar, a double monochromator Brewer and a DOAS/MAX-DOAS spectrophotometer installed at the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics in Thessaloniki, Greece. The aerosol species are modeled with the Optical Properties of Aerosols and Clouds (OPAC) database which provides the optical properties per aerosol mode. They are calculated from Mie theory assuming spherical particles with the exception of mineral dust species for which spheroid particles are assumed. Hygroscopic growth calculations are included and the corresponding optical properties are selected using relative humidity profiles currently from radiosondes and in the future from models as well. The algorithm currently compiles a lookup table of mixtures that constitute of up to four aerosol modes and identifies the mixture/mass concentration combinations that best describe the lidar attenuated backscatter profiles. In the next phase, these profiles will be imported to a radiative transfer model and the combination that best reproduces ratios between the direct solar radiance, sky radiance, and irradiance spectra measured from the spectrophotometers will be isolated.

1 Introduction

Suspended particles are omnipresent in the atmosphere and greatly vary both in terms of size and chemical composition. Their impact on earth's climate, human societies and ecosystems is evident. Not only do they affect human health but they also interact with shortwave solar and longwave terrestrial radiation in complicated ways. Naturally, the combination of different aerosol species produces different outcomes. For example smaller particles are easier to inhale than larger ones and the aerosol toxicity also varies with the aerosol type (Kelly and Fussel 2012). Furthermore, dust and soot particles rather absorb than scatter solar radiation producing a heating effect locally, in contrast with sea salt particles (e.g. Hess et al. 1998). Therefore, monitoring the particle composition and size is just as important as quantifying their load. In-situ instruments can provide the aerosol load composition and size distribution in great detail near the ground. Remote sensing techniques on the other hand can provide information on distant atmospheric regions that are otherwise costly and challenging to reach. Synergistic approaches among passive and active remote sensing instruments have been shown to increase the amount of information one can get (e.g. Chaikovsky et al. 2016). For instance, lidar instruments excel at identifying the vertical distribution of the aerosol load with a spatial resolution of a few meters (Weitkamp 2005). Photometers, on the other hand, can get precise information on the aerosol size distribution and refractive index (e.g. Holben et al. 1998) by gathering angular radiance information from the direct and diffuse solar spectra. In this manuscript, we present the concept of a novel synergistic technique that combines lidar and spectrophotometer measurements. While the scientific literature is rich in lidar and sunphotometer synergies (e.g. Lopatin et al. 2013, Chaikovsky et al. 2016), this is not the case for spectrophotometers since that are currently utilized primarily for the detection of trace gases. Recent studies have shown the capability of DOAS/MAX-DOAS systems for aerosol retrievals as well. In the proposed technique we search for the combination of aerosol species concentration profiles that best reproduces primarily the lidar attenuated backscatter profiles and also the direct solar radiance, sky radiance, and irradiance UV-VIS spectra collected by collocated spectrophotometer measurements.

2 Methodology

The proposed technique for the retrieval of aerosol species profiles utilizes columnar spectrophotometer data and vertically resolved lidar signals. The development is based on a dataset that consists of collocated lidar, Brewer spectrophotometer, and DOAS/MAX-DOAS system data. More details are included in section 2.1. The algorithm deploys a lookup table (LUT) using mixtures generated from pure aerosol species as modeled by the OPAC database (Hess et al. 1998, Koepke et al. 2015). The compilation of the LUT is discussed in section 2.2. Finally, the retrieval technique itself is presented in section 2.3.

2.1 Data

The dataset upon which the algorithm is being developed includes measurements performed at the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics (LAP), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece (40.5 °N, 22.9°E; 50 m). LAP is a member station of the PANhellenic infrastructure for Atmospheric Composition and climatE chAnge (PANACEA, <https://panacea-ri.gr/>) and the testing dataset is based on combined measurements that were performed in the station during the first PANACEA summer campaign that took place between 10th of July and 10th of August 2019. The dataset includes a wide range of atmospheric conditions, with extreme aerosol cases and moderate cases of local pollution. In total, 14 daytime measurements, out of which 12 were collocated with sunphotometer, and 7 nighttime measurements were performed.

Lidar measurements were performed by the THELISYS lidar, operated at LAP and also part of the European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (EARLINET) since 2000 (Siomos et al. 2018). The lidar data processing that includes all necessary signal corrections (dead time correction, dark signal correction, photon and analog signal gluing, range correction, smoothing) has been performed using the Semi-automated Universal Lidar Algorithm (SULA) developed at the National Observatory of Athens (a relevant publication is under preparation). The input products for the Aerosol Species Separation Algorithm (ASSA) include the total elastic attenuated backscatter profiles at 355nm, 532nm, and 1064nm and also the cross polarized elastic attenuated backscatter profile at 532nm. Profiles are provided above 800m that corresponds to the overlap of the system and up to an altitude above which aerosols exist only in insignificant amounts. This altitude is commonly referred to as the lidar reference height. Consequently, the end of the profile always corresponds to a molecular, aerosol free region. Finally, the profiles are downsampled to an effective resolution of 100m. This is done to decrease the number of points and consequently the processing time of ASSA.

Brewer #086 is a type MKIII double monochromator spectrophotometer (Kerr et al., 2010). It is mounted on an one-axis tracker (azimuth) and the entrance prism can move on the zenith. It provides spectra in the range of 290-365.5 nm with 0.5 nm spectral resolution. The instrument operates automatically. The input products for ASSA include the measurements of the calibrated direct and global irradiance spectra in the range of 320-360nm, where the effect of trace gases compared to aerosols is negligible. The global spectra are being calibrated every 1-2 months via measurements of 1000 W calibrated lamps in the dark room of LAP. There is also a weekly stability check using 50 W lamps and, finally, an intensive stability monitoring by the internal 20 W standard lamp, which is automatically measured several times a day (Garane, et al., 2006). The direct spectra calibration depends on the global spectra calibration. Spikes, and irregular spectra are removed algorithmically and the final product contains cloud and quality flagging.

MAX-DOAS measurements have been performed during the campaign with a 2D Phaethon-type system, also installed at LAP. The system comprises a low stray-light AvaSpec-ULS2048LTEC ($f = 75$ mm) spectrograph, the entrance optics and a two-axis tracker (Drosoglou et al., 2017). The spectrograph covers a spectral range of 300–458 nm, uses a 50 μ m wide entrance slit and has a spectral resolution of ~ 0.4 nm Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM). The entrance optics are mounted on a two-axis tracker with two stepping motors controlling the azimuth viewing angle ($0^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 360^\circ$) and the elevation angle ($0^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$) with pointing resolution of 0.125° . The instrument operates automatically and is controlled using custom-made software. A measurement cycle starts with recording of scattered sunlight spectra at elevation angles of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 15, 30 and 90° (zenith) for each azimuth angle. During the PANACEA campaign, the MAX-DOAS system was configured to measure four consecutive azimuth angles: 142, 185, 220 and 255° .

For all instruments used in this work, we utilize only data that are directly collected from the instruments and result from mere proper calibration. We avoid using any inversion products because they include their own a priori constraints that could affect our retrievals.

2.2 Mixture database

ASSA will identify the aerosol mixture per vertical level that best reproduces the measurements. The primary species in the mixtures are modeled according to OPAC. The database includes optical and microphysical information such as the refractive index, the size distribution, the phase matrix, and the single scattering albedo. Up to eight aerosol modes can be externally mixed: water solubles, insolubles, soot, accumulation and coarse mode sea salt, and nucleation, accumulation and coarse mode mineral dust. Spherical particles are assumed for all, except for the mineral dust species that are modeled as spheroids (Koepke et al. 2015) and change state of light polarization. In the current testing phase of the algorithm only four species profiles are retrieved simultaneously to decrease the level of complexity and processing time. Similarly to Hara et al. 2018 we selected water soluble, soot, coarse sea salt, and accumulation mode mineral dust as the fundamental primary modes since these are expected to have the largest contribution in the aerosol extinction (e.g. Hess et al. 1998). In the future, we plan to increase the number of species that are retrieved simultaneously targeting all eight modes. Hygroscopic growth calculations are included in OPAC for 8 relative humidity classes (0%, 50%, 70%, 80%, 90%, 95%, 98%, 99%) for the water soluble and sea salt species. The corresponding optical properties are selected using relative humidity profiles from local radiosondes performed in the airport of Thessaloniki (SKG), 13 km from LAP. Mixtures are generated as follows. Initially, the relative extinction contribution at 355nm to the total extinction of the mixture is considered. We prefer to use the extinction ratio instead of the mass concentration mixing ratio because some aerosol types such as soot can be a minor component in terms of concentration but a major one in terms of extinction as it has a much higher mass extinction efficiency than e.g. coarse dust. For hygroscopic particles this ratio corresponds to the ambient extinction that includes the water uptake. The extinction at 355nm is preferred over other optical properties here because it produces actual measurable effects in the measurements of all instruments described in 2.1 as all of them operate in the UV. An extinction ratio scale of 0 to 1 with equal ratio steps is defined. The step is currently set at 0.1 and corresponds to the mixing resolution of the LUT. To get each valid 4-component mixture, all combinations of 4 numbers selected from the scale (0 to 1 with step 0.1) are produced. Then, only the combinations whose sum equals to 1 are isolated as they can represent actual extinction ratios. In order to switch to concentration space a mapping is required (Eq. 1).

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & (1-f_1)Q_1+f_1Q_2 & \dots & (1-f_1)Q_1+f_1Q_n \\ (1-f_2)Q_2+f_2Q_1 & 0 & \dots & (1-f_2)Q_2+f_2Q_n \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ (1-f_n)Q_n+f_nQ_1 & (1-f_n)Q_n+f_nQ_2 & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (1-f_1)Q_1 \\ (1-f_2)Q_2 \\ \vdots \\ (1-f_n)Q_n \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Here f_i is the extinction mixing ratio, c_i the concentration mixing ratio, Q_i is the extinction efficiency at 355nm while i represents each primary species of a specific mixture. As a result we get a list of 286 unique mass mixing ratio combinations that constitute the LUT. Apart from the mixing ratios, some optical properties are also included in the LUT because they are required to construct the attenuated backscatter lidar profiles. These are the mass backscatter and extinction efficiencies at 355, 532, and 1064nm per mixture and also the cross polarized mass backscatter efficiency at 532nm. The mixture mass backscatter/extinction efficiency is the sum of the efficiencies of each component weighted by the respective mass mixing ratio.

2.3 Methodology

The algorithmic procedure is summarized in Figure 1. The algorithm first tries to reconstruct the lidar attenuated backscatter profiles by iterating over the LUT and over a number of predefined mass concentration levels per LUT entry. Currently 200 equidistant levels in a logarithmic scale ranging from 0.01 to 1000 $\mu\text{gr m}^{-3}$ are assumed. The attenuated backscatter profiles are normalized by the corresponding value at reference height. The mixture scans begin from the end of the profile and proceed downwards. The lidar equation is used for the reconstruction of the attenuated backscatter (Eq. 2).

$$S_j(\lambda, z) = [b_{j, aer}(\lambda, z) + b_{j, mol}(\lambda, z)] \exp \left\{ 2 \int_{z_0}^z [a_{aer}(\lambda, z) + a_{mol}(\lambda, z)] dz \right\} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Here S is the simulated attenuated backscatter signal, z_0 is the reference height. z is the altitude (always smaller than z_0), λ is the wavelength, j represents the polarization type (total or cross), a/b are the extinction/backscatter coefficients respectively, and aer/mol correspond to aerosols/molecules respectively. All molecular profiles are provided by SULA that utilizes the radiosonde temperature and pressure profiles. The constructed attenuated backscatter is normalized by the molecular backscatter value at the reference height to make it directly comparable with the respective measured normalized profiles. For each vertical level, the residuals of the constructed versus measured values for the four lidar attenuated backscatter values are calculated per concentration-mixture combination. The first N combinations with lowermost residuals correspond to best potential solutions. N is currently set to 10. The procedure is repeated down to 800m and 10 values per vertical level that best reproduce the lidar measurements can be retrieved. This is the current development status of ASSA (step 1 in figure 1).

Fig. 1. This flowchart demonstrates the input and output of ASSA. BRW, LDR, and SPR stand for Brewer spectrophotometer, lidar system, and DOAS/MAX-DOAS system, respectively.

In the second step, the profile that best reproduces the measured Brewer and DOAS/MAX-DOAS spectra will be isolated. The library for radiative transfer libRadtran will be applied in order to reproduce the spectra. LibRadtran is already coupled with OPAC which makes current retrievals easy to integrate. The aerosol profile certainly affects the direct solar radiance in terms of the total spectral aerosol extinction. The effect on the global radiance and angular diffuse sky radiance is far more complicated and requires this kind of radiative transfer modeling.

3 Summary

We propose a novel synergistic algorithm to retrieve the vertical concentration profiles of individual aerosol species using lidar and spectrophotometer measurements. User defined parameters that affect processing time by increasing the number of iterations are: the vertical resolution of the lidar profiles, the mixing resolution, the total number of primary species that are separated simultaneously, the predefined concentration levels, and the number of best potential solution that are accepted per vertical bin. Currently, ASSA identifies 10 mixture solutions along with their respective total mass concentration per vertical level that best reproduce the lidar attenuated backscatter profiles. The mixtures constitute from up to 4 primary species including water soluble, soot, coarse mode sea salt, and accumulation mode mineral dust particles. In the next phase, the radiative transfer library lidRadtran will be applied to reproduce spectra that are comparable with the Brewer and DOAS/MAX-DOAS measurements in order to narrow down the potential solutions to a single profile that best reproduces the measured spectra. Sources of uncertainties in ASSA include the general resolution of the retrieval that is constraint, the presence of aerosols that are not considered in OPAC (e.g. pollen and volcanic

particles), internal mixing between aerosols that is not currently taken into account, and finally, the uncertainty of the measurements themselves, which is planned to be included in the future in order to quantify the number of best solutions more objectively. The synergistic potential of the method is rather high since it can simultaneously facilitate trace gases profiling. DOAS/MAX-SOAS systems can provide trace gas profiles given that a priori vertical aerosol information is available. Consequently, better knowledge of the aerosol concentration and composition will result to improved trace gas profiling in the future.

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